

Influence of Media Programmes on Consumers' Behaviour in Nigeria

Lucas Nduka Oluka¹, Chibueze Kelvin Obi², Augustina. N. Ezeh³

¹Department of Political Science,

²Department of Mass Communication,

³Ph. D, Department of Business Administration,

^{1,2,3}Novena University, Ogume, Delta State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The pertinence of advertising lies in its modest efforts to create awareness, inform and persuade target audience (the public) of the availability of a product or service. Producers communicate their brands through this medium. Service providers on the other hand showcase their services to the public to attract patronage. Nonetheless, advertising messages in recent times are apparent in everyday life in various media platforms and attract wider audience especially when a popular artist or personality is involved. This study, therefore, examines the influence of media programmes on consumers' behaviour in our contemporary Nigerian society, where different products and services are fighting with one another for higher patronage and to get number one position in consumers' minds. The study also examines the individual consumer's exposure toward domestic and multinational products advertisement when the services of popular artists and stars are employed. The effect of advertising on consumers' purchasing behaviour is also a focus. The study adopts qualitative research method, which means that data utilized were obtained from secondary sources such as books, journal articles, internet sources, etc. Relevant literatures obtained from these sources are used to establish opinions and perceptions of several researches to the importance of this study. Our findings reveal among others, the relationship between advertisement of products and services, and consumer purchasing behaviour in the country. Suggestions and recommendations are also made to enable both the producers and consumers satisfy their needs and wants after the sales and consumption of commodities.

KEYWORDS: Media programme, Consumers' behaviour, Advertisement, Artists, Stars, Nigeria

1.1. INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that advertising generally has a very long history and existed even in the ancient times in form of signs that showcase wares in market places. The term "advertise" was derived from a Latin word "advertere" which means "to turn toward or to take note of". Certainly, the messages passed on during adverts are intended to attract wider audience to products and services. As a communication tool, advertising is used to create awareness, inform and persuade target audience especially now that modern technology is used in advertising. Its major objective is to sell a product which may be good or service. In the 19th century, it assumed pertinence more than it was in the ancient times, especially as adorable individuals were now employed to showcase these products or services in media platforms (Ogunlade, p. 1).

It suffices, therefore, to say that the influence of media in advertising cannot be underestimated in our contemporary age since it influences people's behaviour on what to purchase or not to. In this civilised age dominated by the powerful forces of globalisation such as technological revolution and economic liberalisation, the mass media has remarkably impacted on product advertising and

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consumption. It has equally affected consumers' behaviour and relationships in various ways, be it between celebrities and ordinary people or between celebrities themselves and their loved ones. In essence, the media manipulates and influences, persuades and pressurises the society, as well as controls the world in positive and negative ways, mentally, physically and emotionally.

With the advent of internet and World Wide Web (WWW), advertising has also taken another dimension with particular interest in product advertisement in social media platform (Ogunyombo et al., 2017). According to the Social Media Marketing Industry Statistics (2008) cited in Ogunyombo et al. (2017: 245), social media has also changed the way marketers conduct their businesses. Reasons abound for consumers' ratings of brands on social media platforms. Although a lot of the target audience are young people exposed to information and communication technology (ICT), Enahoro (2009) observes that youths constitute the majority of internet users, hence, are more influenced by "E-Commerce or Social media" marketing. With this, the public is made to believe everything it is told and not question it. So it is with consumer behaviour, with it being so easy to assert

an opinion so easily after a few taps. Essentially too, the media and internet influence people's careers and change their perceptions about a product within a flash. It also manipulates people in the spotlight to lead their lives in a particular way or to rebel against what they should have been like, and to purchase or not to purchase (Enahoro, 2009).

In Nigeria, modern technology such as electronic media, cable TV channels, as well as new media, like social networks, have made E-Shopping, especially Jumia among others, to be developing rapidly in the country (Anyanwu et al., 2018). The world has become a *global village* and the vision of a *global village* has brought the world closer than ever, increased *global trade*, and is promoting different *cultures' conflict*, blending and promoting cultural communication (McLuhan, 1964). Nigeria's culture has also been affected by the Western culture because nowadays advertisers in the country, as well as foreigners, promote domestic and multinational brands, and give them global cultural touch. That is why local and multinational companies are using the global strategies in advertisements to promote their brands in the country.

Accordingly, the services of TV celebrities, movie actors, famous athletes and personalities, who are liked and respected by target audience, as well as those with attributes like pleasant appearances, extraordinary life styles or unique skills, are employed by these companies to advertise their products and services. Zabid et al. (2002) opines that using a well-known star as an endorser could help to improve the subject's rating of the advertisement, commodity or services. This is why domestic and multinational companies in the country use well-known Nigerian stars in advertisements rather than nameless spokespersons. In addition, famous Nigerian artists and stars that have appeared in special events, such as movies, movie award nights, special screening, news, fashion shows, magazines, tabloids etc. appear in corporation's brands advertisements. This, in fact, has become a universally accepted standard (Joshi & Ahluwalia, 2008; Balakrishnan & Kumar, 2011).

In Nigeria, the government through her agencies, the Advertising Practitioner's Council of Nigeria (APCON), National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) and the National Broadcasting Commission (NBA) regulates the type and quality of product to be publicly advertised. Alcohol advertising in particular is very sensitive, hence, guidelines are provided to promote social and accepted moral behaviour. The law specifically provides that radio, television or print media advertisements of alcohol beverages shall not be permitted in children's programmes. Sportsmen and expected mothers are also not permitted to be used as models to advertise such products (Akpotaire, 2017). In other words, food and drugs cannot be advertised in the country unless they are registered with NAFDAC and advertisement must also receive per-clearance and approval from these agencies before advertisement is done. The focus of this study, therefore, is to examine the extent to which Nigerian consumers like the famous stars and the products they advertise. The study also focuses on whether people recall product advertisement at the time of shopping and remember for a long time the product identity that is promoted by Nigerian stars, celebrities or personalities.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the influence of media programmes on consumers' behaviour in Nigeria. While the specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the extent to which artists or personalities have influenced or changed the behaviour of consumers, their styles and interests towards Nigerian products,
2. Examine the level of consumers' purchasing behaviour towards Nigerian products; and
3. Proffer useful recommendations that will benefit both the producers and consumers in the country.

1.3. Research Questions

To give direction to this study the following questions were raised:

1. To what extents have Nigerian artists or personalities influenced the behaviours, styles and interests of consumers towards Nigerian products?
2. What is the purchasing behaviour of consumers towards Nigerian products?
3. What are the useful recommendations that will benefit both the producers and consumers in the country?

1.4. Research Methods

This study was based on theoretical review, thus the researchers depended solely on qualitative research method to arrive at the conclusions made in the study. This implies that the researchers derived data from secondary sources such as textbooks, journals, periodicals, magazines, newspapers and internet materials to arrive at conclusions made in the study.

2.1. Empirical Review:

2.1.1. Personalities Influence and Consumers' Buying Behaviour in Nigeria

The essence of this review is to provide the perceptions or views of scholars in connection with the influence of famous athletes, movie actors, TV celebrities, personalities, stars and artists endorsement on customer buying behaviour in Nigeria. It appears that the consumer is the central point, and all the marketing activities revolve around him since he is the person who uses the product or service. Manufacturers, thus, produce what he wants and employ the services of famous stars or personality to showcase their products, as well as attract his attention and influence his purchasing habit. Famous stars are those who are well known and popular among a large proportion of a particular group of people. The attributes with which they are connected are attractiveness, talent, and exceptional lifestyle (Taleja, 2008).

In other words, advertisers often choose these personalities as advertising strategy to communicate the attributes of their product, brand or service to consumers. Zabid et al. (2002) found that using a well-known star in advertising could help to improve the subjects' rating of the advertisement, product and service. In this globalised age, this approach appears to increase advertising across all media types, and it is seen that both the domestic and multinational companies located in the country prefer the services of Nigerian stars in advertisements of their products and this in turn impacts on the consumption pattern or behaviour of the people. Advertisers on the other hand are not only promoting the brand but also building brand image and identity among the consumers (Sherman, 1985; Levin, 1988).

Various studies selected within this literature represent consumers purchasing patterns. Literatures are also reviewed here to actually examine the influence and effects of these personalities in advertising and supporting of various products in recent times. Balakrishnan and Kumar (2011) cited in Shoaib et al. (2012:643) posits that celebrity endorsement in advertising enhances product information, creates awareness among consumers and influences their purchasing behaviour. Joshi & Supreet (2008) opines that the advertising strategy of celebrity in the right circumstances can justify the high costs on this form of advertising, and create a very favourable impact on consumers and a connection to a consumer buying habits towards a product(s).

Urde (1994) also in Shoaib et al. (2012: 643) opines that increased attention and brand liking depend on the image of the spokesperson and the impact he or she provides on the consumers. This also influences the purchasing behaviour and brand loyalty on the parts of the final consumers. Ego (2017) points out that some people purchase a product or employ the services of a service provider because of the character involved in advertising the product or service. He also notes that a spokesperson's influence could be affected by other factors like price, similarity of competing brands and availability of other information. To create effective messages, celebrity recruiters must also consider the attractiveness of the spokesperson (McCracken, 1989). Solomon (2002) also states that the advertiser's attractiveness or physical appearance, personality, sympathy and similarity with the receiver, i.e. the perceived social value of the source, also influence consumer behaviour.

When a celebrity endorses a product successfully, consumers will evaluate the endorsement positively, feeling it is credible, believable and appealing (Ohanian, 1990; 1991). As a consequence, people would tend to like the advertisement, brand name, and advertisement recall would be enhanced. Increased product liking and other positive effects may also occur (Brown & Stayman, 1992). According to Ike (2015), an appropriate use of a celebrity is a powerful tool or technique to effect consumers' behaviour towards a particular product type in the country. This is a winning formula to producers in building brand images. Today, the use of celebrities for advertising has become a trend and a winning strategy for corporate image building and product marketing in the country. In short, it has become a prevalent form of advertising in the country as well.

2.1.2 Consumers' Purchasing Behaviour and the Nigerian Products

As stated earlier, consumers are a vital part of the economic process of any society. Without consumers, there will be no market since they patronise economic services and commodities. The Oxford Advanced Learner's dictionary defines a consumer as a person who purchases goods and services for personal use. For Dalyop (2017), a consumer is an individual or organization that patronises economic services or commodities. Consumer buying behaviour, thus, refers to the buying habit of the final consumers or user of a product. In our contemporary age, business organisations have made the study of consumer buying behaviour a priority in order to get close to consumers as well as to understand how and why they buy, and to influence their buying habits. According to Schifinan and Kanuk (2009)

cited in Chukwu and Enudi (2018), consumer purchasing or buying behaviour connotes mental, emotional and physical activities that people engage in when selecting what to purchase in order to satisfy their needs and desires. It is also defined as a combination of consumer buying behaviour and consciousness and external incentives which are likely to result in behaviour remodeling (Miebaka et al., 2017).

Product packaging apart from personality influence is another factor identified to influence consumers' purchasing behaviour in the country. This simply means the wrapping material used on a product in order to contain, identify, protect and display the product. It is also used in recent times to increase sales, as well as to promote the product in the country. Findings revealed that Nigerian buyers are attracted by well branded and packaged product. All things being equal, a well packaged product is likely to attract high patronage. Since vital information about the product is passed through its labels, it is also likely to attract high patronage especially when a well known artist or personality is used to showcase the product and demonstrate its quality (Adeola, 2017).

In Nigeria like any other nation of the world, consumers' buying behaviour is also influenced by buyers' economic and social status, and cultural factors. In other words, income, expenditure patterns, prices of products, complementary and substitute goods, are determined by economic status of the individual buyer, while social influences such as family size, friends, neighbours and associates at work also influence one's purchasing behaviour. On a daily basis, consumers are confronted with tens of images and voices on television, radio; and magazine, newspapers, websites, as well as billboards, showcasing their brands and to steal at least, consumers' unsuspecting attention, as well as to inform them of their products or brands (Ike, 2015). This is done in persuasive manners that positively change the attitudes and behaviours of their targeted audience or anticipated buyers towards their products. Most often consumers' behaviours are also influenced by product packaging complemented by personality or celebrity endorsement.

Sometimes too, consumers' satisfactions are drawn from the public view of the personality showcasing the product and not necessarily the quality of the product itself; this occurs though in real cases especially after a test of such product or commodity. Since there are numerous products, as there are numerous consumers, consumers in the country evaluate products based on their respective prices especially when they serve the same purpose, desire and satisfaction. This implies that the price of a product influences the demand of the product. From our findings, it is evident that the buying habit or behaviour of a buyer is influenced by his economic status too. Those with high wages or the rich go for products with the best quality and packaging, while the poor or low income earners go for those with moderate prices, and sometimes do not bother much about the packaging. This shows that personality influence sometimes, only account when the potential buyer's income can afford the purchase of the product or service. Poor buyers may desire a particular product but their income is a barrier to their taste, no matter how they are attracted by the personality showcasing the product on media platforms.

3.1. Conclusion

Consumers in the country often watch product advertisements or programmes on television or other media outlets. They are often influenced by the advertisers or the appearance of the celebrities they are familiar with. Consumers also feel good and confident when they use products promoted by these Nigerian stars. They think that these famous stars are important aspects of adverts because they elaborate product features in a better manner, and are also seen as popular icon, attractive and familiar among people as well. Therefore, appropriate association between celebrity and product is an important thing, as it creates a good impact, builds a brand identity and convinces more and more people towards the product. Nigerian stars, to some extent, keep refreshing the brand identity, change the interest and style of people. Advertising of brands by these personalities keep the identity of products refreshed in the minds of consumers as well as persuade and encourage them towards the brand while people also retain the product that is promoted by Nigerian stars for a long time and easily recall at the time of shopping, as compared to foreign stars.

4.1. Useful Suggestions and Recommendations that will benefit both Producers and Consumers

The following suggestions and recommendations are proffered to benefit both producers and consumers;

1. It is obvious that a good numbers of Nigerians have internet connectivity and are exposed to other forms of social media platforms. Producers are therefore encouraged to exploit this opportunity to showcase or advertise their brands or products to the public who are already addicted to these platforms.
2. It is also obvious that the purchasing or buying behaviour or habit of Nigerians is influenced by brand packaging, prices, social status, peer influence, as well as celebrity endorsement. Producers should therefore continue to respect these factors in order to sustain the huge patronage they have been enjoying.
3. E-commerce platforms popularity such as Jumia, etc. launched in the country, have in no small measures influenced and promoted marketing strategies. Producers and retailers, therefore, are encouraged to exploit these platforms to communicate their products to the public or consumers. The anticipated consumers are also encouraged to exploit the advantages provided by these media platforms to demand for goods and services they desire with appropriate prices.
4. Shopping online has been found to be reliable and stress free in recent times. Producers and retailers, therefore, are advised to continue to employ this platform to sell their products. Consumers, on the other hand, should continue to build on their trusts and confidence in these platforms which have provided convenience in demand and supply processes in our domestic market.

References

- [1] Adeola, O. (2017). Effect of Product Packaging on Nigerian Consumers' Behaviour. A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of Bachelor Degree of Business Management/Entrepreneurship, School of Business Management and Entrepreneurship, American University of Nigeria, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria.
- [2] Akpotaire, U. (2017). Nigeria's advertising Laws, Regulations and Guidelines: The Simple "Don'ts".

August 9. [Online] Available: nlipw.com/nigerias-advertising-laws-the-simple-donts/

- [3] Anyanwu, G., Okorie, N, & Abiodun, S. (2018). Online Advertising Influence for Promoting Preference for E-Shopping in Nigeria: A Study of Jumia. *Academy of Strategic Management journal*, Vol.17, Issue 6
- [4] Balakrishnan, L. C & Shalini K. (2011). Effect of Celebrity Based Advertisements on the Purchase Attitude of Consumers towards Durable Brands: A study with reference to the city of Chennai. *World Review of Business Research*, 1(2): 98 – 112
- [5] Chukwu, B. A. & Enudi, T. O. (2018). The Impact of Product Packaging on Consumers' Purchasing Behaviour in Benin Metropolis, Edo State Nigeria. *International Journal of Economic, Commerce and Management*, United Kingdom, Vol.VI, Issue 4, ISSN 2348 0386. [Online] Available: <http://ijecm.co.uk/>
- [6] Dalyop, S. R. (2017). A study on the personal factors influencing Nigerian consumer buying behaviour. Research Project in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Award of the Degree of B.Sc Accounting, American University of Nigeria, School of Business and Entrepreneurship.
- [7] Ego, N. (2017). Mass Media Development in a Developing Country: The Nigerian Experience. *AEJAC Journal*, 3:38-51.
- [8] Enahoro, A. (2009). The Role of Stakeholders in promoting safe Internet among Youths. *Journal of Communication and Media Research*, 1(2) 45-60.
- [9] Ike, B. B. (2015). Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumer Brand Preference of Selected Beverage Brands in Nigeria. A Dissertation Presented to the Department of Marketing in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Award of M.SC Degree in Marketing. (Unpublished).
- [10] Joshi, V., & Supreet, A. (2008). The Impact of Celebrity Endorsements on Consumer Brand Preferences, Department of Business, Manipal University, Dubai: United Arab Emirates
- [11] Levin, G. (1988). Celebrity licensing gets tougher. *Advertising Age*, 59(1): 63
- [12] Miebaka, D. G., Nwiepe, N. M. & Kpune, H. N. (2017). Consumer Behavioural Pattern and Patronage of Made in Nigeria Bags (A Survey of Bags Producers in Rivers State, Nigeria). *IIARD International Journal of Economics and Business Management ISSN 2489-0065, Vol.3, No. 2* [Online] www.iiardpub.org.
- [13] McCracken, G. (1989). Who is the celebrity endorser? Cultural Foundation of the Endorsement Process. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 16(3): 310 –321
- [14] McLuhan, M. (1964). *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man*. New York: Signet.
- [15] Miebaka, D. G., Nwiepe, N. M. & Kpune, H. N. (2017). Consumer Behavioural Pattern and Patronage of Made in Nigeria Bags (A Survey of Bags Producers in Rivers State, Nigeria). *IIARD International journal of Economics and Business Management*, ISSN 2489-0065 Vol.3 No. 2 [Online] Available: www.iiardpub.org.

- [16] Ogunlade, B. A. Advertising Design Development in Nigeria: Towards Understanding Advertising Functions and its Psychological Effects, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria.
- [17] Ogunyombo, O., Oyero, O & Azeez, K. (2017). Influence of Social Media Advertisement on Purchase Decisions of Undergraduates in Three Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Communication and Media Research (JCMR)*, Vol.9, No.2, 244-255. (October, 2017)
- [18] Ohanian, R. (1990). Construction and Validation of a Scale to Measure Celebrity Endorser's Perceived Expertise, Trustworthiness and Attractiveness. *Journal of Advertising*, 19(3): 39-52.
- [19] Schiffman, L. G. & Kanuk, L. L. (2009). *Consumer Behaviour*, New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India
- [20] Sherman, S. P. (1985). When You Wish Upon a Star. *Fortune*, 138, 66-73
- [21] Shoaib, M., Bilal, M. Z., Iqbal, Hassan. & Sher, F. (2012). Mass Media and Consumer Purchasing Behaviour: A Case Study of Lahore, Pakistan. *Academic Research International*, Vol. 2, No. 2. [Online] Available: www.journals.savap.org.pk
- [22] Solomon, M. R. (2002). *Consumer Behaviour: Buying, Having, and Being*. (5th Ed). New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [23] Urde, M. (1994). Brand Orientation- A Strategy for Survival. *Journal for Communication Marketing*, 11(3): 18-32. Cited in M. Shaib, M. Z. Bilal, A. Iqbal, S. A. Hassan & F. Sher (2012). Mass Media and Consumer Purchasing Behaviour: A Case Study of Lahore, Pakistan. *Academic Research International*, Vol.2, No. 2. [Online] Available: www.journals.savap.org.pk
- [24] Zabid, M., Abdul, R., Jainthy, N. & Samsinar, M. S. (2002). Perceptions of Advertising and Celebrity Endorsement in Malaysia. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 7(4): 535-554

